

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF CONTINUOUS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the pedagogical and psychological foundations of continuous inclusive education. It analyzes teachers' professional competence, individual approach, psychological environment, and students' integration in inclusive learning. The research results show that to ensure continuity in an inclusive environment, pedagogical approaches, psychological support, and cooperation with parents play a crucial role.

Keywords: inclusive education, continuity, pedagogical approach, psychological foundation, cooperation.

UZLUKSIZ INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada uzluksiz inklyuziv ta'lim tizimining pedagogik va psixologik asoslari yoritilgan. Inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchining kasbiy kompetensiyasi, individual yondashuv, psixologik muhit va o'quvchilarning o'zaro integratsiyasi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, inklyuziv muhitda uzluksizlikni ta'minlash uchun pedagogik yondashuvlar, psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash va ota-onalar bilan hamkorlik muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: inklyuziv ta'lim, uzluksizlik, pedagogik yondashuv, psixologik asos, hamkorlik.

НЕПРЕРЫВНОЕ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ: ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются педагогические и психологические основы системы непрерывного инклюзивного образования. Анализируются профессиональная компетентность учителя, индивидуальный подход, психологическая среда и интеграция учащихся в процессе инклюзивного обучения. Результаты исследования показывают, что для обеспечения непрерывности в инклюзивной среде важно использовать педагогические подходы, психологическую поддержку и сотрудничество с родителями.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, непрерывность, педагогический подход, психологическая основа, сотрудничество.

LOG IN

The professional skills and methodological approach of the teacher are of crucial role in the effective organization of inclusive education. A teacher is not only a giver of knowledge, but a leading person who has a deep understanding of the student's personality, taking into account his psychological features. In this regard, it is necessary to improve the preparation of teachers

for inclusive education, to develop their pedagogical competence through special trainings, seminars and professional development programs.

Digital technology is an important tool in improving inclusive education. For example, access to education for students with disabilities will be expanded through interactive platforms, online lessons, special multimedia programs. At the same time, technology facilitates the individualization, assessment and analysis of the educational process. In the process, the teacher not only uses technical means, but also harmonizes them with psychological support.

Psychological services are an integral component of inclusive education and serve to ensure mutual understanding, positive attitudes, and adaptation among students. As a result of joint work of psychologists, defectologists and speech therapists in educational institutions, the direction of individual development of students is identified. In this way, each child can choose the pace of learning that suits his or her ability in the learning process.

Parents are also recognized as active participants in inclusive education. Their regular communication with teachers, their role in supporting the psychological state of children is invaluable. In a family environment, the values of the student's personality, positive self-assessment and motivation are formed. Therefore, providing psychological and pedagogical advice to parents, involving them in the educational process is one of the important factors.

In addition, creating a motivational environment in inclusive education is of great importance. By acknowledging students' small achievements, involving them in team work, forming an atmosphere of mutual respect, their interest in learning increases. True inclusivity is ensured only when every student feels like an equal member of the community.

And the psychological foundations serve to form self-confidence, positive relationships, emotional stability in students. The stability of the psychological environment is ensured by the interaction of all participants in the inclusive group — the student, the teacher and the parents. The use of psychological support, motivation and individual psychodiagnostic methods plays an important role in the process of social adaptation of students.

To ensure continuity in inclusive education, it is necessary to maintain continuity between the stages of the education system. This is achieved, first of all, through the consistency of the curriculum, constant monitoring of the dynamics of student development and the application of an individual development plan at each stage. The professional skills and methodological approach of the teacher are of crucial role in the effective organization of inclusive education. A teacher is not only a giver of knowledge, but a leading person who has a deep understanding of the student's personality, taking into account his psychological features. In this regard, it is necessary to improve the preparation of teachers for inclusive education, to develop their pedagogical competence through special trainings, seminars and professional development programs.

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To ensure continuity in inclusive education, it is necessary to maintain continuity between the stages of the education system. This is achieved, first of all, through the consistency of the curriculum, constant monitoring of the dynamics of student development and the application of an individual development plan at each stage. Psychological and educational services offer students personalized support.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a continuous inclusive education system is a complex but necessary process that ensures equality of opportunity for every child. A combination of pedagogical approaches, psychological support and social cooperation can fully realize the personal and intellectual potential of each student. Continuous inclusive education will lead the education system of Uzbekistan on a more human, democratic and innovative direction.

A continuous inclusive education system embodies the principles of humanism, equality and justice in society. In this process, the professional potential of teachers, psychological stability and culture of cooperation are important. Therefore, ensuring continuity in inclusive education guarantees an improvement in the quality of education.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Hamidov B. Inclusive education: theory and practice. – Tashkent, 2022.
2. Ismoilova G. Psychological approaches in inclusive education. – Bukhara, 2023.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5712 of April 29, 2019.
4. Rakhmatullayev Sh. Current literary Uzbek language. – University Press, 2006.
5. UNESCO. Inclusive Education Guidelines. – Paris, 2021.